

Chemical analysis of groundwater at some selected sites in Jaipur

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Abstract : The results of a 16-month continuous study on the chemical analysis of groundwater with respect to pH, conductivity and concentrations of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NO_3^- , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , HCO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , F^- , SiO_2 and heavy metals viz. Fe, Co, Cu, Pb, Ni, Zn, Mn at five selected sites in Jaipur are presented. Although at four sites the nitrate concentrations exceed the permissible limits recommended for potable water, at one site the nitrate concentration is unusually high.

Keywords : Ground water, dissolved anions and cations.

In Jaipur city, which is the capital of the Rajasthan State, and situated in semi-arid region, the major source of drinking water is groundwater. Recently high nitrate concentrations have been reported in groundwater samples of walled city and its periphery¹. Since the nitrate is responsible for causing blue baby syndrome – a condition of respiratory failure in babies having excessive nitrate² in their diet, serious and long term studies on groundwater quality are required. Most of the groundwater quality studies^{1,3} carried out so far in this region are concerned with the determination of pH, total hardness, salinity and some common ions only and are limited in scope. Moreover, the determination of heavy metals, which form an important water quality parameter, appears to have not been carried out so far. In this paper we report the results of 16-month continuous study on groundwater analysis.

Experimental

For this study, five different sites in southern part of the Jaipur city were selected. Site A is situated adjacent to a slum in a densely populated locality and due to lack of sewage system, waste water is discharged in underground septic tanks or in open earthen drains. Site B is at the slope of sparsely populated Jhalana hill, the lower end of which houses a industrial estate and at about 25 meter from the site the wastewater of the area flows into a nearby low lying earthen drain. Site C is situated in a thinly populated area without a sewage system. Although, Site D is situated in a locality having a sewage system, an unpaved earthen drain flows about 18 meter from the site and, therefore, there are good chances of percolation of

waste water underground. Site E is situated in a sparsely populated area comprising government staff quarters provided with septic tanks and a proper drainage system.

The ground water samples were collected in passive polythene bottles from manually operated hand pumps at an interval of one month for about sixteen months during June 2000-September 2001. For the determination of heavy metals, a portion of the samples was taken out, and to avoid precipitation of iron, a few drops of HCl were added before concentrating.

The bicarbonate was determined by acid-base titrimetry using bromocresol green as indicator⁴⁻⁶. Whereas the chloride was determined using argentometric method, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were determined by EDTA-complexometry⁴⁻⁶. The concentrations of transition metal ions were determined with the help of atomic absorption spectrophotometer⁴⁻⁶. Na^+ and K^+ were determined using a flame photometer⁴⁻⁶. While sulfate was determined as BaSO_4 gravimetrically, NO_3^- was determined spectrometrically using brucine method. Silica and fluoride were determined using heteropoly blue and Megregian Maier spectrophotometric methods respectively⁴⁻⁶. pH and conductance were determined using usual methods.

Results and discussion

The ranges of concentrations and other parameters found in groundwater samples of different sites are given in Table 1. The values of the ratio, $\Sigma[M^{n+}]/\Sigma[A^{n-}]$, where $\Sigma[M^{n+}]$ and $\Sigma[A^{n-}]$ represent the total equivalent concentrations of cations and anions, respectively, lied in the range 0.96–1.07, showing an excellent agreement with

Note

Table 1. pH, conductance and concentration ranges of the ions (mg L⁻¹) in ground water at different sites in Jaipur city

Parameters/ Ions	Site A	Site B	Site C	Site D	Site E	Permissible limit	Trends
pH	7.36–7.80	7.43–7.6	7.40–7.85	7.33–7.55	7.3–7.6	6.5–8.5	
Λ_{obs}	1780–1980	630–740	520–600	920–1040	680–750	–	A > D > E > B > C
Ca ²⁺	200–240	76–92	48–76	88–120	80–92	75–200	A > D > E > B > C
Mg ²⁺	58.3–87.5	12.15–24.8	8.4–19.44	26.7–56	14.6–29.16	100	A > D > E > B > C
Na ⁺	28–35	19–25	22–35	22–36	18–25	–	
K ⁺	3.7–4.7	2.2–2.9	2.2–2.9	2.2–2.7	2.0–2.5	–	
HCO ₃ ⁻	150–298	210–257	240–279	255–295	220–275.9	200	
Cl ⁻	188.9–212	39.77–49.7	14.9–23.2	69.6–86.2	34.8–51.37	250	A > D > E > B > C
F ⁻	<0.5	0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	1.5	
NO ₃ ⁻	330–400	60–130	30–50	160–200	80–120	45	A > D > E > B > C
SO ₄ ²⁻	103–202	8.64–19.0	2.9–14.8	8.44–28.9	8.2–26.0	150	A > D > E > B > C
Cu	0.01–0.04	0.01–0.03	0.01–0.02	0.01	<0.01–0.01	1.5	
Pb	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.10	
Zn	0.60–1.30	0.20–0.90	0.17–0.84	0.15–0.80	0.10–0.27	5.0	
Fe	0.33–1.12	0.45–1.10	0.58–1.09	0.21–0.88	0.12–0.32	0.3	
Mn	0.01–0.03	0.01–0.02	0.01–0.03	0.01–0.02	0.01–0.02	0.5	

the expected ideal value of 1.0. The values of $\Sigma[A^{n-}]$ and $\Sigma[M^{n+}]$ for each site were in agreement with the eq. (1). The values of parameters, a , b (in meq L⁻¹) and

$$\Sigma[A^{n-}] = a + b \Sigma[M^{n+}] \quad (1)$$

correlation coefficients for different Sites were : 2.36, 0.87, 0.99 (Site A); 0.38, 0.94, 0.94 (Site B); 0.34, 0.94, 0.87 (Site C); 2.78, 0.72 and 0.99 (Site D); and 0.80, 0.88 and 0.83 (Site E). The correlation coefficient values indicate a satisfactory correlation and also validate the analytical measurements. As a check, the observed conductance values, Λ_{obs} , were compared with the calculated conductance values, Λ_{cal} , obtained using eq. (2).

$$\Lambda_{\text{cal}} = \Sigma \lambda_i^{\circ} C_i \quad (2)$$

where λ_i° is the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution of the ion, and C_i is the concentration of that ion in eq L⁻¹. The Λ_{cal} are, in general, 15% higher than Λ_{obs} values. This is probably due to the use of λ_i° values⁵, which are always higher than the λ_i values in solutions of finite ionic concentration, in eq. (2). Keeping this in view, the agreement in Λ_{obs} and Λ_{cal} is considered good and this testifies the accuracy of present measurements.

In Table 1, the trends in the variation in different water parameters at different sites are given and a comparison with IS⁷ and WHO⁸ specifications for drinking water shows that at all places Cu, Pb, Zn and Mn are less than the permissible limit and only at sites A, B and C the

upper range of iron concentration exceeds the permissible limit slightly. It also indicates the groundwater to be unpotable at sites A, B, D and E due to alarmingly high nitrate concentrations; with regard to nitrate site C is a border line case. Three major sources of origin of nitrate in ground water are fertilizers, atmospheric deposition and human sewage deposited in septic systems. Since the sites are devoid of any agricultural activity, the seepage of domestic and municipal wastewater appears to be the major source of nitrate in the groundwater.

Among all the sites studied, the groundwater at site A appears to be most polluted as indicated by the high concentration of ions and heavy metals. The unhygienic conditions at site A, which is located in a slum area having open waste water earthen unpaved drains without any sewage system, appears to be the major cause of groundwater pollution due to the seepage of wastewater and pollutants underground. Similarly, the high nitrate at sites B and D is probably due to the seepage and percolation of wastewater from the earthen drains flowing near the sites B and D, although the site D has a sewage system. The high nitrate concentrations at site E appears to be due to septic tanks⁹, which are reported to cause high nitrate in groundwater. The results of this study indicate that the high nitrate concentration in groundwater is found in those areas, which lack sewage system and house slums, and where the wastewater flows in earthen unpaved drains.

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